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Executive Summary

The epigenome is an interface between intrinsic (genetic) and external (environmental) factors influencing cellular behaviour. DNA methylation, defined as the addition of methyl groups on the C5 position of cytosines on the DNA, is a key part of the epigenome which integrates these intrinsic and external factors and records them as a signature on the DNA. Therefore, DNA methylation represents an ideal tool to monitor exposures and, importantly, an individual's response to these exposures.

Here, we have assessed the impact of two important disease risk factors, smoking and human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, on DNA methylation. Smoking is associated with an increased risk for variety of diseases, notably cervical and lung cancer. Cervical cancer is frequently caused by a persistent infection with a high-risk type of the Human Papillomavirus (hrHPV). Even though the disease is preventable, cervical cancer is one of the major causes for female cancer deaths worldwide. It is not well understood why a small fraction of women develop high-grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and invasive cervical cancer (CIN3+) upon infection with a hrHPV. The possible role of the host methylome (DNAm) in hrHPV-mediated disease progression is currently understudied.

We derived a DNA methylation-based smoking signature using cervical samples and assess the signature in a variety of other tissues which confirms the potential to distinguish between smokers and non-smokers. Importantly, the epigenome is dynamic and can be modified by changes in the environment. Smoking cessation led to a reduction in the smoking index, and the smoking index correlated with daily cigarette use, indicating a dose-dependent effect of smoking on DNA methylation, highlighting the potential of DNA methylation to record dynamically exposures.

To assess the impact of HPV on the cervical epigenome, we assessed DNAm changes in a large cohort of women diagnosed with or without different grades cervical neoplasia (CIN) using the latest Illumina Infinium Methylation EPIC BeadChip, probing over 800000 sites across the human genome. We devised a classifier, the "WID-HPV", able to distinguish HPV+ from HPV- women in the subgroup of women without CIN. Interestingly, we found that our classifier performed well for all healthy women, including those that were diagnosed with low-grade CIN, but not for those diagnosed with CIN3+. This may not only have interesting implications for understanding the role of the host DNAm in hrHPV-mediated disease progression, but also opens possible new avenues for the prediction of the risk for developing CIN3+ and cervical cancer screening.

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1 Introduction and Background

The epigenome represents an interface between personal genetic factors and the environment and is ideally positioned for the assessment of various exposures, such as smoking or viral infections. As part of deliverable D8.1, we assessed the impact of two exposures, namely smoking and human papillomavirus infection (HPV) on DNA methylation. Below and throughout this deliverable, we provide separate sections for these two exposures and our work on the respective exposures.

1.1 Smoking

Smoking is an important lifestyle risk factor for a variety of diseases, including cancer^{1,2}, cardiovascular diseases^{3,4}, and neurological disorders⁵⁻⁷. The risk for these diseases may be reduced by smoking cessation, but the detailed dynamics of risk reduction and biological changes as a function of smoking cessation are yet unclear, although cross-sectional studies suggest that mutation load and potentially methylation changes are reversed within few years after smoking cessation^{8,9}. Measures to objectively quantify individual smoking risk and risk reduction have not yet been assessed longitudinally.

Several studies in blood samples have previously identified methylation loci associated with smoking¹⁰⁻¹³, such as CpG sites in the aryl-hydrocarbon receptor repressor (*AHRR*), including cg05575921¹³. Fewer studies have looked at tissues other than blood, however. A 2015 study investigated smoking-related changes in buccal samples and found that smoking-associated changes correlated with DNAm changes in epithelial cancers¹⁴. Whether smoking also alters DNAm in anatomically distant and not directly exposed cervical samples remained unknown.

Here, we assessed DNAm changes in cervical samples and derived a classifier capable to distinguishing between cervical DNAm from smokers and non-smokers. This classifier was then validated in various other tissues which revealed the DNAm signature consistently identified smokers from non-smokers in nearly all tissues.

As part of work package 8, we have assessed the impact of smoking on DNA methylation (DNAm) in a non-exposed sample (cervical sample) and derived an index capable of distinguishing between smokers and non-smokers, thus providing an epigenetic record of exposure. We provide a brief overview of the background and methodology and further describe performance of the new smoking index (Women's cancer risk identification – smoking) in a variety of tissues, highlighting that this novel epigenetic signature is conserved across multiple tissues and importantly, is reversible, as previous smoker showed a reduced index compared with current smokers.

1.2 HPV

Cancer can be caused by specific viral infections. The Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is a small (~7000-8000 bp) circular double-stranded DNA virus from the family Papillomaviridae that infects epithelial cells¹⁵. There are about 200 different HPV types in 5 different genera (alpha, beta, gamma, mu, nu), but only high-risk types of HPV (hrHPV) are linked to epithelial cancers, specifically carcinomas in the cervix, vulva, vagina, penis, anus, head, and neck. hrHPV types are detected in the majority of cervical cancer cases (estimated 99.7% in 1999), with HPV16 being the most prevalent hrHPV type¹⁶. The discovery of the link between cervical cancer and HPV was an important scientific advance (Harald zur Hausen awarded with a Nobel Prize in Physiology and Medicine in 2008) that led to a major reduction of cervical cancer cases each year¹⁷. Despite the existence of a several HPV prophylactic vaccines and regular Pap or HPV-based screening programs in place in especially in developed countries¹⁸, cervical cancer is the second most lethal cancer type in women today¹⁹.

HPV can be sexually transmitted to a woman and will primarily infect basal epithelial cells in the transformation zone between the ecto- and the endo-cervix¹⁵. When the infection persists, these cells can transform and proliferate as cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN). hrHPV physically tethers its genome to the host genome and hijacks certain cellular pathways of its host to evade immune responses, to regulate its gene expression and to link the different stages of viral replication with host epithelial cell differentiation. Cancer formation occurs when hrHPV genomes spontaneously integrate into the host genome, which leads to altered expression of the hrHPV oncoproteins E6 and E7, and eventually to uncontrollable epithelial cell growth, inhibition of apoptosis pathways and host genome mutations²⁰⁻²².

CIN progresses only rarely to invasive cancer and progression typically occurs over many years. Importantly, it remains unclear why only a small portion of women develop CIN3+ and invasive cervical cancers after high-risk HPV infection. At the same time, we are only becoming to appreciate the complex genetic and epigenetic mechanisms underlying hrHPV-host interactions. Here, we addressed possible epigenetic changes occurring at the level of the host DNA methylome upon hrHPV-infection and CIN severity.

Here, we have assessed DNA methylation changes related to HPV infection in cervical samples and define the WID-HPV signature (Women's cancer risk identification – HPV) capable of discriminating between individuals with HPV and uninfected individuals based solely on DNA methylation. We further assess the HPV index in individuals with CIN1, 2, and 3+, a majority of which are all HPV+ve.

2 Methods

2.1. Samples

2.1.1. Smoking

Samples used for development of the smoking index were collected as part of the FORECEE Programme, a European research project aimed at developing new strategies for female cancer prediction. Cervical screening was performed for women aged >18 years across five different European locations, including the Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Norway, and the UK. FORECEE has received ethical approval from the UK Health Research Authority (REC 14/LO/1633) and other contributing centres. Women with either breast, ovarian, or endometrial cancer as well as age-matched controls were included. For the smoking index, only samples from controls were utilized.

Cervical smears were collected with a Rovers cervical brush and stored in PreservCyt solution (ThinPrep). DNA was extracted from cervical samples on a Hamilton Star liquid handling platform using the Nucleo-Mag Blood 200 µL kit (Macherey Nagel, cat #744501.4) with prior modifications for optimal lysis of cervical cell pellets. Concentration and quality absorbance ratios were measured using a Nanodrop-8000 (Thermo Scientific) and extracted DNA was stored at -80°C until further analysis.

2.1.2. HPV

Cervicovaginal screening was performed for women aged >18 years across recruitment sites in the Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Norway and the UK as part of the FORECEE [4C] Programme²³, a European research project aimed at developing new strategies for female cancer prediction. For this analysis, five subsets of women were defined: cytology-negative women without (“HPV-ve”) or with an hrHPV infection (“HPV+ve”), and women diagnosed with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 1 (“CIN1”), 2 (“CIN2”) or 3+ (“CIN3+”; pre-invasive or invasive cancer). Cervical smears were collected with a Rovers cervix brush and stored in PreservCyt solution in ThinPrep pots. Cytology based on the Papanicolaou technique²⁴ was either done locally at the recruitment site, or at UCL in the UK where also the DNA isolation was performed. DNA was isolated with the Nucleo-Mag Blood 200 µl kit (Macherey Nagel, cat #744501.4) on a Hamilton Star liquid handling platform. Concentration and quality absorbance ratios were measured using a Nanodrop-8000 (Thermo Scientific Inc) and the extracted DNA was stored at -80°C until further analysis. High-performance HPV testing and type determination was done with the cobas 4888 platform²⁵.

2.2. DNA extraction and methylation analysis

DNA normalised to 25 ng/ μ L and 500 ng total DNA were bisulfite modified using the EZ-96 DNA Methylation-Lightning kit (Zymo Research Corp, cat #D5047) on the Hamilton Star Liquid handling platform. 8 μ L of modified DNA were subjected to methylation analysis on the Illumina InfiniumMethylation EPIC BeadChip (Illumina, CA, USA) at UCL Genomics according to the manufacturer's standard protocol.

2.3. Methylation data preprocessing

All methylation microarray data were processed through the same standardised pipeline. Raw data was loaded using the R package minfi. Any samples with median methylated and unmethylated intensities > 9.5 were removed. Any probes with a detection p-value < 0.01 were regarded as failed. Any samples with $> 10\%$ failed probes, and any probes with $> 10\%$ failure rate were removed from the dataset. Beta values from failed probes (approximately 0.001% of the dataset) were imputed using the impute.knn function as part of the impute R package.

Non-CpG probes (2,932), SNP-related probes as identified by Zhou et al., and chrY probes were removed from the dataset. An additional 6,102 previously identified probes that followed a trimodal methylation pattern characteristic of an underlying SNP were removed.

Background intensity correction and dye bias correction was performed using the minfi single sample preprocessNoob function. Probe bias correction was performed using the beta mixture quantile normalisation (BMIQ) algorithm. Sample composition (immune cell, epithelial cell) was inferred using the EpiDISH algorithm.

2.4. Index development

2.4.1. Smoking index

For development of the smoking index (WID-smk, Women's cancer risk identification - smoking), only samples from controls who either currently smoked or never smoked were used. Ex-smokers were excluded from index development. This resulted in 574 samples (n=479 controls, n=95 current smokers). These samples were further subdivided 65-35% into a training and internal testing set for index assessment, resulting in a training set of 363 samples (n=299 controls, n=64 smokers) and an internal testing set of 211 samples (n=180 controls, n=31 smokers).

We assessed differentially methylated positions between controls and smokers based on the F statistic (biggest inter-group variability compared to within-group variability) which did not take sample composition into account, as well as epithelial- and immune-specific differentially methylated CpGs. Subsets of the top 30,000 CpGs were then used for training of a classifier using the glmnet R package using either ridge or lasso penalisation with the cv.glmnet function. The models were compared based on their AUC in the internal testing set and subsequently the lasso model based on the top 9000 F statistic CpGs was chosen as it showed the highest AUC and calibration slope closest to 1. The classifier was then finalised on the combined training and internal testing set and further evaluated in several validation datasets.

2.4.2. HPV index

Sample data from cytology-negative women was divided into a subset for training (2/3: n=146 HPV-ve, n= 202 HPV+ve) and a subset for validation (1/3: n=68 HPV-ve, n= 111 HPV+ve) of a linear index “WID-HPV” designed to discriminate between HPV-ve and HPV+ve women. Six ranked lists of CpGs were constructed from the training set by fitting a regression model adjusted for age and estimated immune cell fraction, with each list being a selection of the CpGs most discriminative in the (i) epithelial component, (ii) immune cell component, or (iii) overall, and ranked either by p-value (10000 CpGs) or F-statistic (30000 CpGs). Lasso, Ridge and ElasticNet regression were performed by scanning the ranked lists gradually adding more CpGs as input. Features from each model were extracted using an elastic-net regularization path for logistic regression approach (R package glmnet). The best performing classifier was chosen manually from performance profiles based on out-of-bag estimates.

2.5. Smoking index evaluation datasets

For evaluation of the finalised smoking classifier, we utilised samples from our own studies as well as using raw data retrieved from Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) preprocessed using our standardised pipeline (Table 1).

Table 1. Datasets used for assessment and validation of the smoking index.

Set	Controls			Smoker
	All	Never smoker	Ex-smoker	Smoker
<i>cervical sample</i>				
3C_VALIDATION*	390	249	141	57
BRCA cervical*	211	unknown	unknown	16
<i>buccal sample</i>				
3C_BUCCAL*	519	348	172	59

BRCA buccal*	209	unknown	unknown	16
MRC1946*	121	72	49	31
<i>blood</i>				
BRCA blood*	214	unknown	unknown	16
MRC1946*	121	72	49	31
GSE87648	251	152	99	92
GSE106648	141	141	unknown	138
GSE50660	442	179	263	22
<i>sperm</i>				
GSE114753	78	unknown	unknown	77
<i>bronchioalveolar lavage</i>				
GSE133062	38	unknown	unknown	28
<i>lung adenocarcinoma</i>				
GSE83842	6	unknown	unknown	6
<i>normal lung</i>				
GSE83842	5	unknown	unknown	6
<i>fetal brain</i>				
GSE90871	10	unknown	unknown	14
<i>umbilical cord blood</i>				
GSE64316	10	unknown	unknown	10
<i>oral rinse</i>				
GSE70977	74	unknown	unknown	149
<i>brain</i>				
GSE147040	168	unknown	unknown	53
<i>skin</i>				
GSE90124	196	158	38	126

* datasets provided by UIBK/EUTOPS

3 Results

3.1 Smoking

3.1.1 Description of the index

The finalised classifier consists of 65 CpGs (for details, see Appendix). Notably, 43 of the index CpGs were also present on the Illumina Methylation450k array, enabling potential assessment of the index in public datasets which are frequently using this array.

We assessed the index in cervical samples as well as a variety of other samples retrieved from Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) (see Table 1) are evaluated whether it could discriminate between individuals who were smokers or not.

Figure 1. Performance of the WID-smk to discriminate between smokers and non-smokers in various datasets, including the AUC (area under the curve) and confidence intervals (shaded in grey) (a, b), and looking at individual blood datasets (c, d). Of note, for some datasets, smoking history was not available ie. some current non-smokers may be previous smokers.

This revealed that throughout a variety of datasets, the index discriminated between smokers and non-smokers (Fig. 1). For blood samples, the discrimination was rather low combining all samples but was improved within individual datasets, suggesting potential batch effects (Fig. 1c, d). The index was reduced in ex-smokers compared to current smokers, but higher than that of never smokers (Fig. 2a). The smoking index also increased with increasing number of daily cigarettes in both cervical and buccal samples (Fig. 2b), indicating a dose-dependent effect of smoking exposure on DNA methylation.

Figure 2. **a** Assessment of the WID-smk index in relation to smoking history shows an increased smoking index in ex-smokers compared to never smokers, but values were lower than those of current smokers. **b** Association of the WID-smk index with daily cigarettes.

Lastly, we assessed the association of the smoking index with a cervical smoking-related disease, namely cervical cancer. Comparing controls with individuals with cervical intraepithelial neoplasias grade 3 or above (CIN3+), we found a small but significant increase in the WID-smk index (Fig. 3). As no phenotypical information on smoking status or history was available in this dataset, we were unable to assess this link more closely but smoking has been reported as an important risk factor for cervical cancer and may therefore indicate that a higher number of smokers was present in the CIN3+ group compared to controls. Alternatively, it could indicate that smoking-related DNAm signatures correlates with cancer-related changes as has previously been proposed¹⁴.

Figure 3. The WID-smk index is significantly increased in samples from individuals with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 3 or above (CIN3+) compared to controls.

3.2 HPV

3.2.1 Description of the index

The final chosen classifier used a pool of 500 input CpGs, resulting in 27 nonzero regression coefficients (Lasso regression, epithelial component; Table 2). To predict the index variation due to differences in chronological age and immune cell composition of the obtained cervical smears, a linear regression model was fitted to indices obtained for the HPV-ve control group from the validation subset and used to estimate and subtract confounding variation from the final WID-HPV.

The discriminative performance of the WID-HPV was tested on a CIN-free validation subset of samples not used to train the classifiers (Figure 4), resulting in an estimated AUC of 0.78 (95%CI: 0.71-0.85, Figure 4b).

Table 2. Description of the 27 CpGs from the WID-HPV.

CpG ID	Chromosome location	CpG context	Gene context	UCSC Gene	UCSC Accession
cg05105016	chr15	open sea	gene body	<i>PIAS1</i>	NM_016166
cg18773260	chr17	island	gene body	<i>HOXB7</i>	NM_004502
cg16901621	chr8	open sea	intergenic		
cg19770292	chr5	open sea	intergenic		
cg26296769	chr6	N shore	TSS1500	<i>KLC4</i>	NM_201521
cg25092881	chr10	open sea	gene body	<i>NRG3</i>	NM_001165972
cg00779638	chr9	N shore	5'UTR	<i>AGTPBP1</i>	NM_015239
cg03499324	chr9	S shore	gene body	<i>PSMD5-A</i>	NR_024408

cg14683065	chr10	S shelf	gene body	<i>LRRC27</i>	NM_001143757
cg04308838	chr18	open sea	gene body	<i>TTC39C</i>	NM_153211
cg11952595	chr13	open sea	TSS1500	<i>ARL11</i>	NM_138450
cg15074838	chr6	open sea	TSS1500	<i>HLA-DRA</i>	NM_019111
cg14804593	chr4	open sea	intergenic		
cg05840412	chr13	open sea	intergenic		
cg08355045	chr6	open sea	intergenic		
cg19045773	chr6	open sea	intergenic		
cg22139830	chr2	open sea	intergenic		
cg13893555	chr9	N shore	5'UTR	<i>FBXO10</i>	NM_012166
cg12284518	chr11	N shelf	gene body	<i>VEGFB</i>	NM_00124373
				3	
cg19585676	chr6	S shore	3'UTR	<i>HLA-A</i>	NM_002116
cg26955290	chr17	open sea	gene body	<i>ASGR2</i>	NM_080912
cg12770425	chr6	N shelf	intergenic		
cg23265105	chr5	N shore	1stExon	<i>PCDHB7</i>	NM_018940
cg10473907	chr6	S shore	gene body	<i>HCG27</i>	NR_026791
cg02767777	chr11	N shelf	intergenic		
cg15071481	chr18	N shore	TSS1500	<i>KATNAL2</i>	NM_031303
cg18922214	chr17	open sea	gene body	<i>SLC26A1</i>	NM_001166348
				1	

Figure 4. Performance WID-HPV (adjusted for immune cell composition and women's age) in the CIN-free subgroup of women. **a** Violin and box plots show the performance in the initial training set and the internal validation set. **b** ROC curve and AUC statistics calculated for the internal validation set.

3.2.2 WID-HPV performance in women diagnosed with CIN

The WID-HPV also is elevated in individuals with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) grade 1 (n=166) or 2 (n=90) (Figure 5). Unexpectedly, individuals with CIN3+ (n=257) exhibit WID-HPV scores similar to HPV-ve controls. We therefore hypothesize that our index captures an epigenetic response to viral infection, and

that the lack of such a response is indicative for CIN3+ progression, or may even drive disease progression. Our preliminary analyses (not shown) further suggest a role of apoptosis-driven clearance of HPV-infected cells, absent in the case of CIN3+. Further experimental validation of this hypothesis is ongoing.

Figure 5. Box and violin plots summarizing the WID-HPV indices (adjusted for immune cell composition and women's age) calculated for the different sample groups: CIN-free women without (HPV-ve) and with a HPV-infection (HPV+ve), and women diagnosed with CIN1, CIN2 or CIN3+.

4 Summary

Here, we have presented the WID-smk and WID-HPV index.

4.1 WID-smk

The WID-smk index is a smoking index developed in cervical samples which can distinguish smokers from non-smokers based on methylation in various tissues.

In further work on the tobacco-related exposure, we are now assessing differential effects of smoking on the epigenome in epithelial versus immune cells as well as peripheral versus tissue-resident immune cells and are in process of preparing a publication. Moreover, in an ongoing clinical study part of Work Package 8, we are longitudinally monitoring the influence of smoking cessation on DNA methylation and other biological markers related to health and disease risk, enabling an unprecedented insight into the dynamics of smoking cessation, disease risk, and the ability of DNAm to capture individual risk. In further large-scale studies, the association of the smoking index and future cancer risk may be verified. Additionally, the smoking index may also be useful as a biofeedback monitoring marker for individuals undergoing smoking cessation.

4.2. WID-HPV

We analyzed the genome-wide methylation patterns in a large cohort of women with and without a hrHPV-infection, and that presented with different grades of CIN. A “WID-HPV” classifier was constructed that probes only 27 differentially methylated sites to effectively discriminate HPV-ve and HPV+ve women without high-grade CIN. First, this demonstrates that hrHPV induces changes in the host DNAm of healthy women. Second, since for the majority of the CIN3+ cases these sites showed similar methylation levels to the HPV-ve group, despite the infection with a hrHPV, we propose there is a link with the progression to cervical cancer and these hotspots for hrHPV-induced epigenetic alterations in the host genome. Ultimately, the differentially methylated status of the specific sites summarized by the WID-HPV may be promising targets for the design of cervical cancer screening and risk prediction methods that are non-invasive.

5 References

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6 Appendix

Name	Weight	On 450k array	Gene	Region
cg13612274	-61.23719392	Yes	FOXP3	5'UTR
cg15228671	-37.76733774	Yes	ARL5A	TSS200
cg12483699	-24.24968944	Yes		
cg04270274	-23.01088726	Yes	CNOT1	5'UTR
cg16467105	21.19742369	Yes	NPC2	Body
cg03254102	18.46342555	Yes		
cg03006338	-17.00390843	Yes	CHAF1A	TSS200
cg04559888	-13.78551433	No		
cg17812026	-13.76611970	Yes	SLC43A2	Body
cg12806681	-13.75115595	Yes	AHRR	Body
cg05086879	-9.93349516	No	MGAT3	5'UTR
cg08937674	9.39554526	Yes	PSMA5	Body
cg07596824	8.89899583	No		
cg19122460	8.74399898	Yes	SLC38A3	3'UTR
cg26819916	-7.91576183	Yes	ZKSCAN5	5'UTR
cg17114151	-7.42325742	Yes	PTEN	TSS200
cg18219490	-6.64807626	Yes	PPM1K	TSS1500
cg17496354	-6.03506306	Yes	PLEKHA7	Body
cg05575921	-5.96564370	Yes	AHRR	Body
cg00045592	-5.37507061	No	SLAMF7	5'UTR
cg24154650	5.10183035	Yes	EPOR	Body
cg06036945	-4.66759647	No	AHRR	Body
cg19394142	4.60491786	No	ZC3H3	Body
cg09606208	4.30669486	Yes	PUS10	Body

cg21566642	-3.13293350	Yes		
cg04665124	-3.06053380	Yes		
cg18463340	3.03832992	No	<i>DYSF</i>	Body
cg12850103	-3.00639934	No	<i>MAEL</i>	TSS1500
cg20189916	-2.96252020	Yes	<i>SF3B2</i>	1stExon
cg19025234	-2.89697975	Yes	<i>THBS4</i>	Body
cg08029920	2.63983452	Yes	<i>TMEM82</i>	Body
cg02447733	-2.61739069	Yes	<i>SAPS2</i>	Body
cg03420791	2.34313927	Yes	<i>UBE2I</i>	Body
cg16255816	-2.00266989	Yes	<i>HAP1</i>	Body
cg05261953	-1.88278950	No	<i>NALCN-AS1</i>	Body
cg22440155	1.87249936	No	<i>GNG7</i>	5'UTR
cg04197363	-1.68480424	No	<i>ANGPT2</i>	TSS1500
cg09570566	1.63024493	Yes	<i>SHKBP1</i>	Body
cg14713034	1.55263636	No	<i>KCTD20</i>	TSS1500
cg19532954	1.50244546	Yes	<i>ID3</i>	TSS200
cg16065241	-1.27868035	Yes	<i>DNAJC7</i>	TSS200
cg06644428	-1.25079317	Yes		
cg22625568	1.16224861	Yes	<i>ASFMR1</i>	Body
cg06505213	1.13300467	Yes	<i>SLC35A2</i>	5'UTR
cg17147440	-1.02392996	Yes	<i>TPM1</i>	Body
cg06094323	0.97017103	Yes		
cg03890840	-0.92209486	Yes		
cg20545852	-0.80510943	No		
cg06148480	-0.76484525	Yes	<i>TBR1</i>	Body
cg27208865	0.75521332	Yes	<i>C10orf26</i>	TSS1500
cg23650350	0.72894477	No	<i>OSTM1</i>	Body
cg21509819	0.68121658	Yes	<i>GPR108</i>	TSS1500
cg06885459	0.48632337	Yes	<i>MCF2L</i>	Body
cg04108296	0.44973913	Yes	<i>MPZL1</i>	1stExon
cg25172578	-0.44810608	No		
cg25765275	0.41682616	No	<i>MTCH1</i>	Body
cg21204024	0.40612630	No	<i>GOLPH3L</i>	5'UTR
cg18039373	0.38265917	No	<i>SLC25A42</i>	TSS1500
cg04953612	-0.37345175	No		
cg03944921	0.36445258	Yes	<i>WDR44</i>	TSS200
cg14218885	-0.27089063	No		
cg17239375	0.20376641	No	<i>LINC01170</i>	TSS1500
cg05930965	0.11036208	No		
cg05184938	0.09620502	Yes	<i>SEPT9</i>	5'UTR
cg26004771	-0.08860905	Yes		